

Metal-Semiconductor-Metal Photodetector Based on Porous In_{0.08}Ga_{0.92}N

Authors : Saleh H. Abud, Z. Hassan, F. K. Yam

Abstract : Characteristics of MSM photodetector based on a porous In_{0.08}Ga_{0.92}N thin film were reported. Nanoporous structures of n-type In_{0.08}Ga_{0.92}N/AlN/Si thin films were synthesized by photoelectrochemical (PEC) etching at a ratio of 1:4 of HF:C₂H₅OH solution for 15 min. The structural and optical properties of pre- and post-etched thin films were investigated. Field emission scanning electron microscope and atomic force microscope images showed that the pre-etched thin film has a sufficiently smooth surface over a large region and the roughness increased for porous film. Blue shift has been observed in photoluminescence emission peak at 300 K for porous sample. The photoluminescence intensity of the porous film indicated that the optical properties have been enhanced. A high work function metals (Pt and Ni) were deposited as a metal contact on the porous films. The rise and recovery times of the devices were investigated at 390 nm chopped light. Finally, the sensitivity and quantum efficiency were also studied.

Keywords : porous InGa_N, photoluminescence, SMS photodetector, atomic force microscopy

Conference Title : ICMET 2014 : International Conference on Materials Engineering and Technology

Conference Location : Bangkok, Thailand

Conference Dates : December 24-25, 2014